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Project acronym:

OPTIPATH

Project full title:

Adaptive optical metasurfaces for real-time, label-free and non-destructive 7D digital pathology

HORIZON EIC Grants

HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01

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D 7.1

Website, project logo and social media links

Due delivery date: 31-03-2025

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Organization name of lead contractor for this deliverable:

SINTEF AS

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	X
CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

Deliverable number:	D7.1
Deliverable name:	Website, project logo and social media links
Work package:	7
Lead contractor:	SINTEF AS

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Abstract
<p>This document briefly describes the deliverable D7.1 Website, project logo and social media links. It covers the purpose of the website and gives an overview of the website's technical specifications, layout, functionality and location. It also describes the project logo and social media accounts.</p>

Public introduction ¹
<p>The OPTIPATH project website is dedicated to disseminating the project framework, objectives and key findings. It enhances the visibility of the project's scientific outcomes and communicates the project's methodologies, motivations and events.</p> <p>The OPTIPATH website URL is: eic-optipath.eu</p>

¹ According to Deliverables list in Annex I, all restricted (RE) deliverables will contain an introduction that will be made public through the project WEBSITE

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1 WEBSITE

A public website has been set up, available through eic-optipath.eu and optipath.uber.space. The website is based on Wordpress and is running on servers located in Germany by the company Uberspace. The initial setup of the website has sub-pages for “about the project”, “consortium”, “dissemination” and “contact”. Together, they give a short overview of the project goals and technology, the consortium partners, disseminated results and contact information. The website also links to the project information page on the Cordis website.

To keep the website up to date, we will be posting regular updates on the LinkedIn profile that is then automatically shown on the website front page. Additionally, all disseminated results such as journal articles and popular science outreach will be added to the “dissemination” page. At the minimum, the website will be updated quarterly with relevant progress and will include bi-annual newsletters. All project partners have the opportunity to publish material on the website through SINTEF or can request login information to do so themselves.

Figure 1.1: Screenshot of the home page of the website, which displays a feed from the LinkedIn profile.

2 PROJECT LOGO

We hired a graphical designer to aid us in the design of a project logo: Thøring Grafisk Design.

Several ideas were discussed, including the inclusion of key elements:

- a) Illustration of cells (indicative of pathology)
- b) Rectangular dielectric metasurface pillars (indicative of the radical nanophotonic technologies involved).
- c) A wave of light through the word “OPTIPATH” with the EU color scheme.

Early sketches from the Graphical designer were presented by email correspondence to the consortium and feedback gathered prior to the project kick-off in Oslo on the 20th -21st of February 2025. A summary of the feedback and discussions from the kick-off event were shared with the graphical designer, before the following design was finalized:

(A) Simple version (e.g. headers of documents)

(B) More detailed version (e.g. presentation front-page):

We received files for the logo in file formats EPS, AI and PNG, and elements in SVG and these are located on the project’s SharePoint ready for use when disseminating the project.

3 SOCIAL MEDIA

A LinkedIn profile was created for the OPTIPATH project with the following address:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eicoptipath/>

A profile on X (formerly Twitter) was also created with address <https://x.com/EicOptipath>.

These channels will be used to achieve wider reach of the research conducted. We target regular tweets and LinkedIn posts to foster public interaction. This will also be useful to identify and collaborate with leading players in the field and maximize public outreach.

4 CONCLUSION

The OPTIPATH website, logo and social media were successfully created within the deadline for this deliverable, D7.1, due on 31.03.2025. The website and social media will be continuously updated to include any publications (technical, scientific), public presentations, impactful news, activities calendar, etc.